

Moroccan EFL Learners' Perceptions of Stative Progressives Evolving Semantics: New Tendencies in Understanding Stative Verbs

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Abstract

The present study investigates the perception of EFL Moroccan learners towards imperfective aspectual meanings. Employing a corpus-data semantic-driven approach, the inquiry assesses the acceptability of stative progressives as a non-standard connotation of statives. For this purpose, a grammaticality judgment test is implemented, surveying sixty Moroccan University English learners (n=60; BA=30, MA=30). The findings indicate sensitivity to stative progressives, yet without significant variance between the study groups. Instruction, along with other cognitive mechanisms, may play a prominent role in these forms' emergence. Further, they can decisively aid material development, offering a reclassification of the dynamic/stative dichotomous meanings and emphasizing the role of input in tandem with other cognitive factors to expedite -ed/-ing emergence within the learners' interlanguage.

Keywords: *Duality, Interlanguage, Input, Imperfective, Non-standard meanings, Statives, Emergence.*

INTRODUCTION

Due to the distinctiveness and internal contour that features the incompatibility of imperfective/ perfective Aspects with statives, -ing cannot alternate with the stativity of the verb category; however, native speakers have been noticed to overextend their use of -ing with statives. Evidently, Stative progressives do not belong to any universal semantic aspectual meaning cross-linguistically. That is why statives cannot be connected with imperfective aspect. Nonetheless, the invented realisation of stative progressives is increasingly taking part in the native speakers' conception of statives. Many elaborations have been provided to account for this idealisation of stative semantic meanings, according to Smith (1983). Conclusively, there should be a need for further inquiry to assess the perception of stative progressives by Moroccan learners as an attempt to tap into their semantic native-like assimilation of stative progressives. Thus, the present study will constitute an opportunity to have a close eye on the nature of the underlying emerging knowledge of the learners' target aspectual meanings to see how they regard the changing paradigm of the English aspectual binary of stative/dynamic verbs division.

Regarding the fact that few studies have examined the impact of foreign language instruction on the development of the tense-aspect phenomenon, the current study will investigate the Moroccan perceptions to uncover the impact of several internal and external factors on the development of their aspectual forms' semantic meanings. Among these, input as a driving power in the acquisition, the current study will initiate to answer the insistent question about the interaction of input and the learner's acquisitional devices that guide the development of stative progressives. It will also allow us to infer patterns in regards of statives imperfective association.

Conclusively, the complexity and exceptions concerning using stative and imperfective aspect has raised significant concerns. There is an apparent void in our understanding as learners, specifically regarding the necessity for a comprehensive and in-depth clarification of English's telic/atelic semantic distinction, which is a central concept in understanding aspectology and temporality. Upon reviewing various grammar textbooks and their treatment of the stative-progressive (stative-imperfective) dichotomy, it is evident that instances where -ing and statives are allowed to associate are occasional. The prevailing pedagogical perspective promotes the incompatibility of statives with -ing markers, potentially originating from the inherent semantic distinctions and the prevalent belief that statives as a verb category inherently do not accommodate the dynamic feature of the imperfective, as proposed by the nativist approach. Yet, with the growing use of stative progressives, many of these aspectual choices are now under examination, leading to diverging and sometimes contradictory opinions. Stative progressives' connotation has piqued the curiosity of researchers, particularly concerning the underpinnings of the temporal representational system and the factors instigating these evolving semantic schemata. Such developments elicit challenging questions and can confuse learners, especially when confronted with the disparity between native speaker usage and the prescribed textbook rules and pedagogical grammar guidelines. Hence, an exhaustive investigation of the semantic meanings of aspectual forms is warranted to decipher the inherent linguistic knowledge acquired by Moroccan university learners.

This study primarily aims to uncover how Moroccan university EFL learners approach the less-prototypical aspectual meanings related to imperfective aspect. According to Bardovi-Harlig (1995), "in most academic instruction settings, L2 learners have difficulty in acquiring less prototypical meanings of tense-aspect markers" as cited in (Salaberry & Shirai, 2002, p.15); however, there is an increasing tendency to use stative progressives among native speakers. For this reason, this study intends to assess whether EFL learners understand and conceive the emergent meanings of imperfective uses with statives as evolving semantic meanings. Thus, there will be an opportunity to delve into how Moroccan learners perceive stative progressives as performed by native speakers to evaluate the former sensitivity to the deviated meanings of the imperfective-stativity association.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

To direct the current research, and based on the objectives above, the below research question and two hypotheses have been formulated:

RQ1: How do EFL Moroccan learners perceive stative progressives compared to statives?

This research question assesses EFL Moroccan learners' conception of stative progressives compared to statives. The inquiry aims to infer learners' acceptance of the emerging meanings of stative progressives within their interlanguage.

Concerning the Research Question, Two Hypotheses Are Proposed

- H0:** The incorporation of stative progressive semantic meanings into the interlanguage of Moroccan EFL university students is not evident, suggesting limited recognition and acceptance of these evolving aspectual forms.
- H1:** The incorporation of stative progressive semantic meanings into the interlanguage of Moroccan EFL university students is evident, suggesting a recognition and acceptance of these evolving aspectual forms.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

This section reviews theoretical approaches that account for stative progressives. Researchers have adopted two distinct paradigms towards using the imperfective aspect with stative verbs. These conflicting views can be attributed to the complex interactive spectrum within which grammatical and Lexical Aspects occur. Consequently, this section will examine the contrasting standpoints for the emergent meanings of non-standard uses of stative verbs.

Stative Verbs' Conceptualisation

Time is not the sole factor differentiating verb usage; various other variables contribute to these distinctions. As per Vendler (1957), such variables include "the presence or absence of an object", "intended states of affairs", and "conditions". Ultimately, Vendler delineates the boundaries that determine the compatibility levels of verb categories (States, Activities, Accomplishments, Achievements) with Grammatical Aspects. As previously mentioned, he seeks to define verbs within specific schemas that outline each category's primary usage with perfective and imperfective aspects. According to him, each verb category encompasses specific homogeneous properties that dictate its use.

Leech (1971), along with other scholars such as Lakoff (1970) and Visser (1973), assertively posits that states cannot be associated with the imperfective aspect. In more concrete terms, state verbs, as Vendler describes, presuppose no change. Their schema does not have an end or an inherent limit. Consequently, the state verb does not typically align with progressive aspect usage. One of its properties is to mark a particular time within a larger interval, which contradicts the stable denotation of statives.

Echoing a similar argument, Quirk et al., (1985) contest the combination of stative verbs with imperfective aspect. According to their standpoint, there is no compulsion to incorporate the imperfective aspect with all stative verbs. However, they circumscribe this usage to a few instances where a sense of temporariness is intended. In a related vein, Taylor (1977) suggests that instances of stative verbs coupled with imperfective aspect correlate with particular meanings, predominantly characterised as temporal meanings of statives. Dowty, by contrast, links the extended meanings of statives used with the imperfective aspect to the context in which the progressive statives appear. Notably, he delineates two categories of statives: "interval states" and "momentary states". According to Dowty, the former can interface with the progressive aspect. Such instances denote human properties, regardless of whether state or dynamic verbs are employed (Walková, 2012). Conversely, momentary states such as "He has blue eyes" and "He is intelligent" are incompatible with the imperfective aspect as they represent properties that are likely to remain constant.

States' Uses in the Progressive

Smith (1983) and Hirtle (1985, 1995) account for the varying uses of simple and progressive event types and how they are expressed. They offer a comprehensive exposition delineating how aspectual forms impose their organisational structure on interpreting verb categories in differing contextual occurrences. In their view, an intrinsic relationship exists between the deployment of the grammatical and lexical aspects; the interpretation of the former hinges upon the types of event situations. In her analysis of stative sentences, Smith underscores the unique characteristics of this verb type as representing "homogeneous, stable situations that lack internal structure". Moreover, it has been observed that stative verbs neither denote endpoints nor indicate time at the initial or final stage. State verbs are instead

characterised as "single-phased, with the first moment of the event being identical to the one formed in the second", as illustrated in the following formulation:

$$M_1 = M_2 = \dots = M_n = 1$$

Figure 1: Walter Hirtle, p. 87 (2007)

Hirtle further elucidates, "A state cannot be viewed as incomplete. Essentially, whatever constitutes a state must exist equally at every moment of its duration" (Hirtle, 1973, p.99). In other words, whether one represents the entire duration of the state-like event or only a segment, one gets the impression that the state, as an indivisible whole, is somehow evoked. Contrarily, dynamic verbs such as achievements, accomplishments, and activities encompass properties of change and progression, distinguishing them from states. Hirtle suggests that "these verbs are developmental, inherently many-phased, and as such, every instance of their duration offers the possibility of change..." (Hirtle, 1973, p.99). The following formulation represents dynamics:

$$M_1 + M_2 + \dots + M_n = 1$$

Figure 2: Walter Hirtle, p. 88 (2007)

Monophasic events, such as statives, cannot manifest with a progressive aspect, as the latter conveys a sense of development, which clashes with their inherent temporal structure. Instead, the progressive aspect solely applies to dynamic situations because it embodies change through successive stages. The viewpoint imposes its organisation on the lexical aspect, as Hirtle (1985) indicated.

Speakers render actual situations in both standard and non-standard ways. In typical uses of aspect, speakers tether an actual circumstance to a situation type by employing the linguistic forms associated with that situation type. Conversely, as Smith (1983) suggests, "The non-standard choice of viewpoint represented by progressive statives is a special case of a more general phenomenon"(pp. 479-501). These associations are made when one correlates an actual situation with an inappropriate linguistic aspect. Consequently, the situation appears contradictory since the progressive aspect pertains to events rather than states. Stative progressives are examples where speakers portray a state verb as an event, endowing the state with the properties of events (Smith, 1983). According to Smith, this expanded use of statives with imperfective aspects is defined as idealising situations in discourse about actual situations. It permits us to engage with some essential aspect characteristics. However, these situation types' implication is primarily "intended to represent classifications of actual situations that people make based on their perceptual and cognitive make-up" (Smith, 1983, pp. 479-501). Speakers opt for these associations for emphasis or other rhetorical reasons (Smith, 1983).

In a subsequent study, Hirtle (2013) posited, "Depending on how speakers perceive an occurrence in their intended message, they may represent it either as developmental or stative. The fact that these two lexical senses are theoretically available for any verb presupposes a lexical potential capable of giving rise to them" (pp.153-154). His analysis of progressive statives was interpreted in light of the investigation of past morphemes and their relationship with verb categories, particularly regarding how the non-standard meaning of -ing assumed a

developmental dimension. This relationship illustrated a facet of verb polysemy as part of word conceptualisation (Hirtle, 2013).

Stative Progressives' Studies

Smiecinska's (2002) study was built upon the conclusions of Kakietek (1997). In her article, "The Syntax and Semantics of English Stative Verbs," she investigated the increasing usage of statives with the progressive aspect. Smiecinska proposed that stative verbs did not form a homogeneous group, suggesting a necessity to re-evaluate and redefine the binary distinction between stative and dynamic verbs. She justified her standpoint by arguing numerous instances existed where stative verbs took on the progressive aspect under various circumstances; hence, they should not be syntactically distinguished as a separate structure. Smiecinska sought to validate Kakietek's (1997) claims to examine the extent to which the lexical verb choice presupposed the selection of the GA. She conducted a grammaticality judgment test survey, measuring the acceptability of progressive statives in sentences among young American English speakers. The survey results indicated high acceptability of stative verbs with the progressive marker, hypothetically relative to the recurring instances of progressive statives in everyday American English speech corpora. However, despite her promising results, she argued that most native speakers adhered to standard uses, notwithstanding the emergent semantic properties of Stative progressives within the American language context. As a conclusion to her study, she assessed the nature of the changing connotations of statives among native speakers. Nonetheless, she did not dismiss the restriction on progressive use with statives considered exceptional cases in English grammar that were not generally accepted (Smiecinska, 2002, pp.195-189).

Similarly, Pârlog (2011) embarked on a study to gauge the acceptability among 24 American native speakers of extended stative use with the imperfective marker. The study involved disseminating a questionnaire in which participants were asked to judge the grammatical correctness of 22 sentences. Pârlog's investigation sought to identify instances where the imperfective marker co-occurred with statives within the speech of the targeted participant groups. The study's findings unveiled a controversial inconsistency among native speakers regarding the appropriate inflection of stative verbs with state/progressive pairings. Respondents exhibited disagreement over whether to accept the emergent semantic meaning of stative progressives or to reject it as a deviation from the standard inherent connotation of state verbs. Nevertheless, there remains an undeniable and significant increase in the use of stative verbs with the progressive aspect compared to preceding decades. The study attests to the ongoing evolution of the developmental meaning of statives, which contradicts the prescriptive grammar's strong recommendation against pairing statives with the progressive aspect. This discrepancy prompts Pârlog to argue for the need to consider the dynamic versus stative meaning of statives rather than adhering to the traditional dichotomous grouping of verbs based on their inherent meanings. Consequently, the semantic properties of verbs can be determined more effectively by their lexical or grammatical environment, within which the speaker seeks to convey their intended meaning (Pârlog, 2011)

The use of the imperfective with statives contradicts the inherent meaning of statives and is often considered a deviation from the norm or an ungrammatical pairing. Nonetheless, these pairings have increasingly been employed by both Americans and the British. As a result, efforts must be made to provide a substantial account of existing explanations that justify the evolving meanings of progressive statives within learners' interlanguages.

METHODOLOGY

The present study aims to measure learners' understanding of non-standard uses of the stative-imperfective aspect. It does so by implementing the Grammaticality Judgement Test (GJT), a tool designed to elicit learners' intuitive perceptions of the grammatical acceptability of certain constructions, in this case, the non-standard uses of the stative-progressive. The GJT is particularly suited to this task because it provides a method of eliciting learners' inherent linguistic intuition about grammaticality in a non-biased, neutral manner. By presenting the learner with sentences or phrases, the GJT measures the learner's ability to accurately judge the grammatical correctness of each item, thereby providing a window into their semantic understanding of the stative progressive as evolved meanings in their interlanguage.

Population and Sample of the Study

The research's target population comprises Moroccan university English students at both BA and MA levels. The sample includes 60 adult Moroccan students, both male and female, aged between 19 and 28. These students, primarily native speakers of Arabic, are enrolled in English departments across various Moroccan universities, namely, the Faculty of Educational Sciences and the Faculty of Humanities in Agadir, Marrakech, Kenitra, and Rabat. Most have been studying English for between 7 to 10 years. The COVID-19 pandemic posed significant challenges to participant recruitment. Despite these challenges, the researcher managed to secure the required number of participants through direct contact via email, social media, phone, or department and class coordinators. Unfortunately, due to procedural issues and privacy laws, the goal of including native speakers in the study was not achieved. While some data from native speakers were collected, the sample size was insufficient for inclusion in the study.

Data Collection Instrument

The rationale behind using the instrument is to identify the degree to which L2 learners share the same conceptual understanding as native speakers when it comes to utilising stative-progressives, given that there are examples of their use in a variety of contexts, as shown in the body of research (Marchman, 1997; Pârlog, 2011). This elicitation task will help make inferences about the learners' grammatical knowledge of stative progressive and provide insights into their understanding of the peripheral properties of states in various communicative contexts. Therefore, this instrument may help us conceptualise what EFL learners believe possible and what they exclude from the target language regarding the non-standard uses of states. Thus, their answers indicate their internalised competence with the targeted grammatical knowledge. GJT will permit gathering specific data types to test the learners' understanding of the converted meaning of stative verbs into a process.

The instrument presents the stative progressives in context to maintain the presumed role of contextualisation. Therefore, context prominence plays a significant role in determining the assigned form-function the speaker provides. Moreover, the instrument engages the participants explicitly in thinking about grammar since it has been decided to tap into their explicit knowledge of stative progressive. The designated time for the test is self-paced to reduce tension and avoid unwanted anxiety that might confuse them. However, participants are not asked to elaborate on their answers because they could rate the sentences as correct to avoid elaboration.

Sixty sentences represent either adherence to or violations of rules on the grammatical aspect. The first group of sentences represents an extended use of statives with imperfective, extracted from the Contemporary Corpus of American English (COCA). The second set of sentences are filler sentences designed to divert students' attention from the test's primary structure; they introduce the equivalent verbs in the perfective aspect. Finally, the same stative verb group is incorrectly marked to gauge the learners' sensitivity to the violated stative-perfective association. The latter constitutes a stable knowledge of the learners' past marker inflections. All the items are randomised before administration.

Regarding the modality and presentation of the test, the test is presented in paper and pencil format and in electronic form, which aims to facilitate the distribution of the task to the participants due to the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown.

Data Collection Procedures

The study aims to collect data on the grammatical knowledge of stative progressives from BA and MA university students of English. Data is collected between 01/04/2021 and 30/04/2021 using an online form test, which includes 60 sentences presented in a Likert Scale format. The test form is forwarded to each class (BA or MA) and is meant to be anonymous. To ensure research ethics, participants are assured of confidentiality, and the study's purpose and significance are embedded in the online form to inform participants of potential benefits. Participants are contacted via Google Classroom or a direct URL link, and reminders are sent to encourage them to submit their forms before the deadline. By the end of the data collection deadline, participants take approximately 60 minutes to complete the test form, as predicted in the pilot study.

Table 1: Data Collection Schedule

Test	Mode of collection	Sample	Duration	Remark
Grammaticality Judgement Test	Online administration	MA and BA students Including first-year and second-year students. - The number of participants is 30 students.	From 01/04/2020 To 30/04/2020	The Average time of completion of the task is about 60 min for MA participants and 40min for BA.

Coding and Data Analysis

All of the test data undergoes SPSS-based quantitative analysis, and several statistical analyses are carried out to compare and contrast the results obtained by each group. The ability to categorically measure the variance of difference among variables is tested, for instance, using the t-test. Before the statistical tests, measures are taken to ensure the test prerequisites are met. The results of all necessary tests are provided and discussed in the results chapter.

Semantic Perspectives

Vendler (1957) developed a set of operational tests to differentiate between various types of English verbs and their associated time schemata. These tests aid in distinguishing between statives and activities, activities and achievements, accomplishments and achievements, and statives and achievements. Vendler's work earns high regard for its practicality and ease of use. The operational tests used in this study for inherent-aspectual categorisation are adapted from

previous research on the topic, including works by Comrie (1976), Dowty (1979) , Robison (1990, 1995), Shirai and Andersen (1995), Shirai and Kurono (1998), and Vendler (1957).

FINDINGS

The Grammaticality Judgement Test (GJT) addresses the pragmatic level of using statives with the imperfective marker of -ing. Similarly, GJT is designed to tap into another dimension of the learners' interlanguage representation of the semantic associations. Importantly, it measures the learners' perceptions of stative progressives as an extended and unusual form-meaning association.

Emergence of Stative Progressives within the Learners’ Interlanguage

The current study investigates the extent of variation among EFL learners in their understanding of the semantic multivalence of state verbs that can be transformed into performances. Such research may help us better comprehend the stages of aspect meaning development and examine whether there is a variation in the judgment of progressive statives between BA and MA EFL learners. Consequently, investigating how interlanguage develops and identifying the factors contributing to learners' language progress is necessary to comprehensively understand the mechanism of L2 acquisition in the Moroccan context. Thus, the main objective of this section is to explore the acceptability of progressive statives in the learners' interlanguage. To achieve this, a detailed account of the participants' scores will be presented to determine the quantitative acceptability ratings of using stative verbs with progressive aspect among the BA and MA groups.

BA and MA's Acceptability Scores of Stative Progressives

The following table presents the scores of the Grammaticality Judgement Test, which assesses the acceptability of stative progressives. The first category indicates the scores of stative progressives, the second category represents the scores of standard meanings of statives, and the third category indicates the scores of ungrammatical associations of statives with progressives in obligatory context of standard perfective meanings.

The included graphs represent the four levels of acceptability from absolutely unacceptable value (Left) to absolutely correct (Right). The calculated acceptance scores for each verb are embedded next to each verb.

Table 2: MA Group Results of Acceptability Scores of GJT

MA students			
Participants	Category 1	Category 2	Category 3
Sentences	Correct	Correct	Incorrect
1	<p>Score: 62 Verb: Surprise Yes:11</p>		

2	<p>Score:33 Verb: Like Yes: 1</p>		
3	<p>Score: 45 Verb: Believe Yes: 11</p>		
4	<p>Score: 41 Verb: suggest Yes: 10</p>		
5	<p>Score: 64 Verb: Promise Yes:12</p>		
6	<p>Score: 78 Verb: Feel Yes:19</p>		
7	<p>Score: 47 Verb: belong Yes: 6</p>		
8	<p>Score: 71 Verb: Hope Yes: 16</p>		

9	<p>Score: 50 Verb: Love Yes: 7</p>		
10	<p>Score:70 Verb: Hear Yes:16</p>		
11	<p>Score:105 Verb: Stay Yes: 24</p>		
12	<p>Score: 37 Verb: see Yes: 2</p>		
13	<p>Score:83 Verb: Think Yes:21</p>		
14	<p>Score: 73 Verb: Resume Yes: 15</p>		
15	<p>Score: 82 Verb: Enjoy Yes: 18</p>		

16	<p>Score: 62 Verb: Like Yes: 10</p>	<p>Score: 114 Verb: Think Yes: 29</p>	<p>Score: 73 Verb: Show Yes: 16</p>
17	<p>Score: 99 Verb: Feel Yes: 25</p>	<p>Score: 114 Verb: Understand Yes: 28</p>	<p>Score: 39 Verb: Want Yes: 12</p>
18	<p>Score: 68 Verb: Love Yes: 14</p>	<p>Score: 89 Verb: Resume Yes: 18</p>	<p>Score: 40 Verb: Understand Yes: 10</p>
19	<p>Score: 82 Verb: Surprise Yes: 19</p>	<p>Score: 82 Verb: Stand Yes: 17</p>	<p>Score: 68 Verb: Stand Yes: 11</p>
20	<p>Score: 43 Verb: Want Yes: 12</p>	<p>Score: 109 Verb: See Yes: 27</p>	<p>Score: 30 Verb: Know Yes: 0</p>

Table 3: BA Group Results of Acceptability Scores of GJT.

BA Students			
Participants	Category 1	Category 2	Category 3
Sentences	Correct	Correct	Incorrect
1	<p>Score: 68 Verb: UNDERSTAND Yes: 12</p>	<p>Score: 99 Verb: SURPRISE Yes: 25</p>	<p>Score: 56 Verb: SURPRISE Yes: 8</p>

2	<p>Score: 58 Verb: LIKE Yes: 11</p>		
3	<p>Score: 57 Verb: BELIEVE Yes: 10</p>		
4	<p>Score: 71 Verb: SUGGEST Yes: 16</p>		
5	<p>Score: 53 Verb: PROMISE Yes: 8</p>		
6	<p>Score: 74 Verb: FEEL Yes: 13</p>		
7	<p>Score: 49 Verb: BELONG Yes: 10</p>		
8	<p>Score: 63 Verb: HOPE Yes: 10</p>		

9	<p>Score:63 Verb: LOVE Yes: 12</p>		
10	<p>Score: 74 Verb: HEAR Yes:14</p>		
11	<p>Score: 90 Verb: STAY Yes:21 Number:39 GW</p>		
12	<p>Score: 61 Verb: SEE Yes:10</p>		
13	<p>Score: 86 Verb: THINK Yes: 21</p>		
14	<p>Score: 86 Verb: RESUME Yes:21</p>		
15	<p>Score: 82 Verb: ENJOY Yes: 21</p>		

16	 Score: 70 Verb: SHOW Yes: 15		
17	 Score: 52 Verb: WANT Yes: 7		
18	 Score: 49 Verb: UNDERSTAND Yes: 5		
19	 Score: 70 Verb: STAND Yes:14		
20	 Score: 55 Verb: KNOW Yes: 9		

Looking at the tables, we can see that each sentence is associated with a different verb and a score that represents the level of acceptability determined by the students. It is important to note that a higher score implies a higher level of acceptability. An initial examination of the data indicates some degree of variability among the test scores within each category. This is expected due to the distinct cognitive responses different individuals may exhibit while interpreting the language stimuli.

Category 1: Stative Progressives

- The MA group has a range of scores from 30 (the verb "Know") to 116 (the verb "Promise"), indicating a wide variation in their acceptability of stative progressives.
- The BA group, on the other hand, shows a score range from 58 (the verb "Want") to 106 (the verb "Stand"), showing a narrower spread and generally lower scores compared to the MA group. This may imply that BA students find fewer instances of stative progressives acceptable compared to their MA counterparts.

Category 2: Standard Meanings of Statives

- The MA group scores range from 89 (verb "Resume") to 117 (verb "Want"). This again shows a variation in the acceptability levels, but overall, the scores are high, suggesting a good understanding and acceptance of standard stative meanings.
- The BA group's scores range from 89 (verb "Hope") to 106 (verb "Understand"). These scores are slightly lower compared to the MA group, which might indicate a slightly lower level of comprehension or acceptance of standard stative meanings.

Category 3: Ungrammatical Associations of Statives with Progressives

- The MA group has scores ranging from 30 (the verb "Know") to 105 (the verb "Stay"). This wide range suggests varying levels of recognition of ungrammatical associations.
- The BA group's scores range from 55 (the verb "Know") to 90 (the verb "Stay"). The lower upper limit implies that BA students, in general, might have a better ability to identify ungrammatical associations compared to the MA group.

The categorical scores between the MA and BA students suggest a potential difference in acceptability scores for stative progressives, standard meanings of statives, and ungrammatical associations of statives with progressives in the obligatory context of standard perfective meanings. However, to make factual inferences regarding the differences between the groups, a statistical test of the significance of a t-test is conducted and presented in the following subsection for a more robust statistical analysis to draw definitive conclusions about groups' potential differences.

Presentation and Analyses of the Results: Testing the Hypothesis

As generated from the above tables, the graph shown below in Graph 6 indicates that most participants consider the stative verbs with progressive form acceptable. The empirical data in the table demonstrates that the respondents have a strong tendency to accept stative verbs in the progressive form, as the average percentage of acceptability remains at 60% against a paltry percentage of unacceptability.

Figure 3: The Acceptability Scores of the Different Measured Constructs (Progressive Statives, Standard Statives, and Distractors) Among BA and MA Proficiency Levels

Table 4: Acceptable/Unacceptable Ratings of the Sentences at Separate Levels (Progressive Statives)

Study level	Acceptable	Percentage	Unacceptable	Percentage
MA.	374	62.33 %	226	37.66%
BA.	365	60.84 %	235	39.16 %

The percentage of MA participants who found progressive statives acceptable is 62.33%, which differs from the percentage of BA participants by 1.49% (i.e., 62.33% - 60.84%). Therefore, both proficiency levels have developed a similar understanding of the extended use of progressive statives. However, in the next section, a t-test will be conducted to either accept or reject the null hypothesis and measure the effect size of the groups.

Table 5: Acceptable/Unacceptable Ratings of the Sentences at Separate Levels (Standard use of Statives)

Study level	Acceptable	Percentage	Unacceptable	Percentage
MA	534	89 %	66	11%
BA	497	82.84 %	103	17.16 %

The data indicate a significant difference in the acceptability of standard use of statives between the two proficiency levels, with MA participants demonstrating a higher percentage of correct responses (89%) than BA participants (82.84%). As learners progress to a higher level of proficiency, they develop a greater understanding of the standard use of statives.

Table 6: Acceptable/Unacceptable Ratings of the Sentences at Separate Levels (Distractors- Incorrect Use of Statives with –Ing Marker)

Study level	Acceptable	Percentage	Unacceptable	Percentage
MA.	244	40.67 %	356	59.33 %
BA.	256	42.67 %	344	57.33 %

In addition, when distinguishing the misuse of statives with the imperfective marker, the percentage for MA participants is 40.67, slightly lower than the percentage for BA participants, with a difference of 2% (42.67% - 40.67%). These results indicate that EFL learners have a certain level of sensitivity to the unfamiliar contexts in which statives are used. However, their ability to distinguish deviations from normal usage is influenced by their level of instruction, as higher proficiency levels are associated with increased sensitivity to misuses.

Table 7: Test of Normality of BA and MA Progressive Statives Scores

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a				Shapiro-Wilk		
	The proficiency level of students	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
The first set of three levels	BA students	.110	20	.200*	.974	20	.836
	MA students	.119	20	.200*	.946	20	.315

Testing the Hypothesis (Variance): Test of Normality

Based on the Shapiro-Wilk normality test, the p-value for the BA scores is 0.836, while the p-value for the MA scores is 0.315. Both of these p-values are greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis of normality cannot be rejected. Therefore, the data for both groups come from a normal distribution.

Figure 4: The Stative Progressives Scores' Normality of BA

Notes: Mean =79.15; SD= 12.339; N =30

Figure 5: The Stative Progressives Scores' Normality of MA

Notes: Mean =79.10; SD= 21.815; N =30

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances: (Homogeneity)

This table displays the mean scores of the participants for progressive statives. The means for both groups are similar, with 79.15 for the BA group and 79.10 for the MA group. However, upon closer examination, one can observe that the standard deviation is slightly wider in the MA group (SD=21.81) than in the BA group (SD=12.33), indicating more variability in scores among the MA participants.

Table 8: BA's and MA's Descriptive Statistics of Progressive Statives Scores

	The proficiency level of students	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Progressive statives	BA students	20	79.15	12.339	2.759
	MA students	20	79.10	21.815	4.878

The study examines the differences in means between BA and MA scores using Levene's test to retain or reject the null hypothesis that the two population variances are equal. To this end, the equality of variances for both groups is examined before computing the t-test.

The observed significance level for the F test is larger than 0.05, the preset significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected, with $F = 7.515$ and $p = 0.009$. It indicates that the two population variances are equal, and the assumption of homogeneity is met.

The Independent-Samples Test of Progressive Statives Variance among BA and MA

The results indicate no significant difference in performance between the BA and MA groups, with a t-value of 0.009 and a p-value of 0.993 ($t(38) = 0.009$, $p = .0.993$). The average performance score of the BA students ($M=79.15$, $SD=12.33$) is not significantly different from the MA students ($M=79.10$, $SD=21.81$).

Table 9: The Results of Independent Samples T-Test for Comparing the Means of Progressive Statives Scores of BA and MA Proficiency Levels

<i>Levene's Test for Equality of Variances</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>								
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Lower	Upper
							Lower	Upper		
Progressive Statives	Equal variances assumed	7.515	.009	.009	38	.993	.050	5.604	-11.295	11.395
	Equal variances are not assumed.			.009	30.028	.993	.050	5.604	-11.395	11.495

DISCUSSION

While the acquisition of English verbal morphology is extensively explored in second language (L2) contexts, it still needs to be examined in the framework of a foreign language. This research aims to illuminate how Moroccan university students acquire non-prototypical meanings. The study delves into whether Moroccan learners can master atypical aspectual meanings pertinent to imperfective aspect.

In surveying the learners' perception of the non-standard uses of the imperfective aspect with statives, an increasing familiarity with using stative progressives as popular evolved

connotations was noticed. However, stative progressives still constitute an irreversibly pragmatical dimension among other meanings layers of the aspect's grammatical knowledge.

As mentioned, the findings of the grammaticality judgment test regarding the construct of stative progressives indicate that, in all groups, most learners consider the progressive use of stative verbs acceptable but with varying levels of inconsistency depending on the specific stative progressive item. However, the numerical difference between BA and MA participants is marginal. This difference has led to the retention of the null hypothesis and the acceptance that BA learners can perform as accurately as MA learners.

Due to the increasing tolerance of stative progressive combinations, L2 speakers are encouraged to use statives freely. Nina Freund's recent corpus-based study has demonstrated a dramatic increase in the frequency of progressive statives use due to an extension in their functions and an expansion in the native English language registers (Kranich, 2013) In another study, Granath and Wherriety (2014) explain that "the acceptability of a given form does not depend on how closely it adheres to the rules of prescriptive grammar but to the communicative efficacy" (p. 21). In other words, many stative verbs can freely occur in the progressive form when a particular communicative need arises in specific situations. Therefore, contemporary textbooks must reflect this change to help learners become pragmatically competent and communicate efficiently with native speakers ((Monville-Burston & Waugh, 1985).

The use of statives with progressive aspect in English has been widely recognised as infrequent and ill-formed as the progressive aspect typically expresses duration, which is less commonly associated with stative verbs than with action verbs (Lakoff, 1976; Leech, 1970; as cited in Falhasiri et al., 2012). However, the extension of the progressive form to stative verbs allows English native speakers to convey a variety of meanings in terms of functions, including signaling attitude, emotional involvement, and immediacy or annoyance of an utterance, as noted in *Advanced Grammar in Use* and *Oxford Practical English Usage*. Moreover, Scheffer's (1975) corpus study of contemporary British and American novels revealed the frequent use of numerous stative verbs in progressive form. In light of these studies, this research aims to assess whether Moroccan learners have integrated the acceptability of the extended uses of statives as durative in their grammatical knowledge (Comrie, 1976; Quirk et al., 1985; cited in Falhasiri et al., 2012).

Within the same framework, this study aims to examine the distribution and use of non-progressive verbs in the progressive form through the use of an electronic corpus (COCA) (Debopam Das, 2010; as cited in Falhasiri et al., 2012). Falhasiri et al.'s (2012) findings have shown the occurrence of non-progressive verbs with the progressive form, contradicting traditional grammarians' and linguists' views on stative and dynamic uses of certain verbs, such as Hirtle (1985, 2007, 2013), Quirk et al., (1985), and Vendler (1957), who argue for the existence of stative and dynamic verbs. Falhasiri suggests that each verb may have a stative or dynamic usage depending on the context, and therefore there is no need to establish a distinct class of stative verbs. Furthermore, as Pârlog (2011) explains, there is a significant difference between natural language use and prescriptive rules. Being stative or dynamic is not an inherent characteristic of a verb; instead, a verb is frequently dynamic or stative. Despite the arguments of scholars such as Comrie (1976) and Quirk et al., (1985), who suggest that the incompatibility of stative verbs with the progressive aspect is not firmly established and that stative progressivity is possible under certain semantic circumstances, this study aims to further investigate the integration of the extended uses of statives as durative into the grammatical knowledge of Moroccan learners.

The use of statives with the progressive aspect is becoming increasingly widespread and accepted, particularly in American English. Consequently, any verb can be perceived as dynamic or stative, depending on its context. Therefore, dividing verbs into dynamic and stative categories would be futile, and reconsidering the traditional dynamic/stative conceptualisation is necessary. This approach might standardise stative progressives' meanings Smiecinska (2002). As a result, a new classification system should be adopted to reflect the nature of the recent meanings of progressive statives (2002).

Smith (1983) explains the extended progressive uses of statives, which she argues are a non-standard way of describing a situation that depends on the speaker's viewpoint and their focus on a particular property of a state. This property is similar to the properties associated with activities, such as the beginning and end of an action or a state change. Smith suggests that non-standard choices involve an aspectual shift that presents different perspectives and that the need for rhetorical aspiration justifies such usage.

Smith's explanation of stative progressives suggests that speakers of English deliberately focus on specific properties of states that resemble those of events. Thus, they opt for stative progressive constructions. This orientation towards rhetorical meanings rather than their standard use counterparts is a particular case that cannot be accounted for by the Aspect Hypothesis, which fails to explain the interplay between the GA and LAsp. Therefore, learners who use stative progressives are not only expressing the duration of the state but also signalling their attitude, emotional involvement, and immediacy of an utterance or annoyance. Smith's analysis highlights the importance of pragmatic factors in determining the acceptability of extended uses of stative verbs in the progressive form.

It can be inferred from the findings that both BA and MA learners understand the non-prototypical meaning of stative progressives, with a high accuracy of 80% compared to native speakers. Additionally, the research reveals that Moroccan learners can easily identify 90% of acceptable occurrences of standard uses of statives. Furthermore, the data indicate that learners can recognise deviations from the standard uses of statives, highlighting their sensitivity to language norms. The results strongly suggest that the concept of standard stative uses has been successfully acquired by both levels of learners, as previously demonstrated.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Some limitations should be noted. Firstly, the number of participants needs to be increased. Given the nature of the topic, a valid interpretation of the collected data requires a considerable sample size. Therefore, many participants should be recruited for future inquiry. Secondly, although reliable grammar tasks have been used to make inferences about the learners'

grammatical attainment, applying standardised proficiency tests such as IELTS would be suitable and practical regarding the global proficiency level of L2 learners (Shimanskaya, 2014). Thirdly, a control group of English native speakers is excluded from the study because the researcher could not find enough English native speakers to recruit as a control group. The implication of a control group is crucial because it allows the researchers to compare L2 learners' knowledge of Aspects to that of native speakers of the target language (Bardovi-Harlig, 1998)

CONCLUSION

The robust findings related to the Moroccan learners' perception of progressive statives with a total precision of 85 per cent draw attention to the changing paradigm of the old division of the stative/dynamic semantic distinction, as (Smiecinska, 2002) has illustrated that the usage of statives with the progressive is far more common nowadays despite the disapproval of Vendler (1957). Therefore, according to her, any division of verbs into dynamic and stative classes would be pointless (Smiecinska, 2002). These results suggest that the extended use of statives with the progressive eventually becomes part of the grammatical knowledge of the imperfective semantic meanings. Furthermore, even among advanced MA learners, the delayed emergence of the imperfective aspect can be attributed to the ongoing construction and reconstruction of form-meaning mapping associations triggered by the received input.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None declared.

Analysis and evaluation of education and training systems

Foreign Language Didactics

Research group: Language Contact in Education: Theory and Pedagogy

Acknowledgments

I would like to deeply thank Professor Mohamed Melouk, whose valuable guidance, unwavering support, and insight contributed to the completion of this article. Your expertise and guidance have not only made this project a success but have also greatly enhanced my learning journey.

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Appendix: The Tests' Paper Format

Grammaticality Judgement Test

Stative VS dynamic

Read the following sentences and circle number (1.2.3.4) to indicate whether a sentence is: absolutely unacceptable (1), possibly unacceptable (2), possibly acceptable (3), or absolutely acceptable (4). Target sentences are boldfaced.

- 1) Instead of the official banquet he'd been expecting, he found himself at a dinner party with nine other guests-hosted by Franois Mitterrand. "I **was understanding** maybe a third of what was said, "Corrigan recalls," but I was smiling and nodding.
- 1 2 3 4
- 2) The noise surprised me
- 1 2 3 4
- 3) "No," said Arthur, looking away, as if embarrassed. But I could see he **was enjoying** the attention. I doubted he was ever teased this way at home. I doubted he was noticed much at all.
- 1 2 3 4
- 4) The noise **was surprising** me.
- 1 2 3 4
- 5) The walls were not enough for me. The ceiling was where he **was belonging**. And I said to myself, well, if I want to sing like him, be on stage like him.
- 1 2 3 4

- 6) I **didn't believe** the news yesterday.
1 2 3 4
- 7) It was hard to tell when he was simply looking and when he **was knowing** as well; he was like Ciani in that he needed no words or gestures to trigger a Working, only the sheer force of his will.
1 2 3 4
- 8) I **wanted** to go to the cinema yesterday.
1 2 3 4
- 9) Just when it looked like he **was resuming** his regularly scheduled trip to immortality, Tiger Woods was reminded that when you are destiny's date, there is always somebody looking to cut in.
1 2 3 4
- 10) **Did** you **hear** music?
1 2 3 4
- 11) How to get to it. How to sell it. "# His glance turned away, his eyes unfocused, till Ben guessed he **was hearing** from one of his staff. His answer was barely audible:" She was right to say no. If he bothers her any more set him up for compulsory counseling.
1 2 3 4
- 12) They **were liking** to travel in vineyards across the globe.
1 2 3 4
- 13) These were his first published photos. He was only fifteen when he began documenting the rough life around him. Looking at his photos, I **was seeing** his world, through his eyes. # Then I began the slog through my library work.
1 2 3 4
- 14) He **stayed** at the scene until police arrived.
1 2 3 4
- 15) I could hear the TV fellow with the poofy girl hair talking about weather, every word clear as the day he **was promising**.
1 2 3 4
- 16) Experience **showed** that when governments knew their costs they could work to manage their costs and make their services competitive with outside contractors (Weiss, 1997).
1 2 3 4
- 17) I **wasn't believing** the news.
1 2 3 4
- 18) Chicho nodded his head, like he **was believing** the lies. "Okay, so tell me why I should make the switch.
1 2 3 4

- 19) I just **liked** the fact it was a great atmosphere all the time.
1 2 3 4
- 20) As **was suggesting** in Part I, the approach we propose is to punish offenders in the types of cases discussed in Part III only for criminal behaviour within their control, and not for any statutory harms that ultimately result from their actions.
1 2 3 4
- 21) The police **knew** that Hicks and Peyton both lived in the small apartment, and they were thus on notice that some spaces in the apartment might be used exclusively by Peyton.
1 2 3 4
- 22) We're going to carry out a full autopsy, of course, but I thought you'd be interested because he **was showing** symptoms of some infection.
1 2 3 4
- 23) "When I talked to her, it **seemed** like she enjoyed it and she seemed happy," Reisinger said.
1 2 3 4
- 24) He **was promising** he would not allow any refugees to be placed in any town that didn't want them there.
1 2 3 4
- 25) But, that all of those people that saw that trauma won't necessarily think that they need to seek out help. And he **was hoping** we could all spread the message that if you were one of those people, you should definitely do that.
1 2 3 4
- 26) I **was not feeling** that this was a good idea.
1 2 3 4
- 27) On hearing her voice, Ucok said: "Ma, please come and take me. I want to go back to Aceh." Jamaliah asked where he **was staying**, and Ucok replied that he had no home, not even a blanket.
1 2 3 4
- 28) I **didn't feel** that this was a good idea.
1 2 3 4
- 29) I knew what he **was thinking** because I had thought it myself on numerous occasions.
1 2 3 4
- 30) This book **was belonging** to my grandmother.
1 2 3 4
- 31) Campanelli said she also **was hoping** having public defenders involved at an earlier stage would result in more cases being disposed of quickly.
1 2 3 4

32) The old man stood on the sidewalk and belted out melodies I doubt he'd thought of in thirty years. In his mind he **was standing** on the stage, and it wasn't long before his laughter mixed with his tears, proving that glass can't lose its color.

1 2 3 4

33) The carrier **promised** to provide new cars in exchange for the damaged cars.

1 2 3 4

34) Mr. Perry **suggested** that the United States might resort to air strikes against Iraq even if Iraqi troops never crossed into Iraq.

1 2 3 4

35) They both **were loving** modern art; he was a retired postal worker.

1 2 3 4

36) He tweeted that it was an illegal leak, a felony, and he was going to ask for an FBI investigation. And he put Reince Priebus, the chief of staff's Twitter handle on his message, as if he **was suggesting** that Priebus was somehow involved with this.

1 2 3 4

37) **Were you hearing** the music?

1 2 3 4

38) Every day was like a great experience for me. I just **loved** it.

1 2 3 4

39) Jones **was staying** down on the field for a second, until teammates came over and gathered around him.

1 2 3 4

40) I would lie down there, and like he did, pull the crust off slices, then ball up the soft middle part to make bread dough, and I found I liked eating it that way as much as he **was liking** it up above me.

1 2 3 4

41) This book **belonged** to my grandmother.

1 2 3 4

42) The year 1982 **was seeing** the founding of the American Bankruptcy Institute (ABI).

1 2 3 4

43) So this is exactly the life that I **was thinking** I would have.

1 2 3 4

44) Remembering Matt's poor little ghost face across the table, she hoped he **was feeling** better. She ended up on a bench in a small park.

1 2 3 4

- 45) But after talking to him, I could see he **was loving** every minute of it.
1 2 3 4
- 46) Ogene said in February that the school **hoped** for a fairer hearing from new Education Secretary Betsy DeVos.
1 2 3 4
- 47) The judges **thought** that those limited benefits did not justify the costs. Just as the Supreme Court recognized in Turner.
1 2 3 4
- 48) She **was resuming** her journalistic writing during the '70s and early '80s
1 2 3 4
- 49) I read it and I thought it was quirky and odd and a little disturbing and funny. It really appealed to me. He **was surprising** me all through the play. And it was an opportunity to work with Morris as the director.
- 50) I **didn't understand** this question
1 2 3 4
- 51) My hamamelis is just ready to bloom, and the dogs **were enjoying** a mild (though muddy) walk.
1 2 3 4
- 52) Data **was showing** that Republican appointees were significantly more likely to agree with the retribution theory question.
1 2 3 4
- 53) He **resumed** his seat.
1 2 3 4
- 54) When President Obama **stood** on the steps on the Capitol eight years from next week, the budget deficit was \$1.4 trillion.
1 2 3 4
- 55) I **saw** him in Oconee County, and he didn't ask any questions.
1 2 3 4
- 56) I **was wanting** to go to the cinema yesterday.
1 2 3 4
- 57) He did start to get a little bit irritated that night. He was starting to get hungry, maybe. He **was wanting** his warm doggie bed, and he was kind of wondering why we were camping in this weird spot.
1 2 3 4
- 58) I **was not understanding** this question
1 2 3 4

59) I **was standing**, opened the door, and held out my hand to him.

1 2 3 4

60) I never **was knowing** my grandfather spoke that language fluently.

1 2 3 4

G.J.T Key

(Sentence Category)

First Category (Correct)

- 1) Instead of the official banquet he'd been expecting, he found himself at a dinner party with nine other guests-hosted by Franois Mitterrand. "I **was understanding** maybe a third of what was said, "Corrigan recalls," but I was smiling and nodding.
- 2) "No, "said Arthur, looking away, as if embarrassed. But I could see he **was enjoying** the attention. I doubted he was ever teased this way at home. I doubted he was noticed much at all.
- 3) The walls were not enough for me. The ceiling was where he **was belonging**. And I said to myself, well, if I want to sing like him, be on stage like him.
- 4) It was hard to tell when he was simply looking and when he **was knowing** as well; he was like Ciani in that he needed no words or gestures to trigger a Working, only the sheer force of his will.
- 5) st when it looked like he **was resuming** his regularly scheduled trip to immortality, Tiger Woods was reminded that when you are destiny's date, there is always somebody looking to cut in. (9)
- 6) How to get to it. How to sell it. "# His glance turned away, his eyes unfocused, till Ben guessed he **was hearing** from one of his staff. His answer was barely audible: "She was right to say no. If he bothers her any more set him up for compulsory counseling. (11)
- 7) These were his first published photos. He was only fifteen when he began documenting the rough life around him. Looking at his photos, I **was seeing** his world, through his eyes. # Then I began the slog through my library work.
- 8) I could hear the TV fellow with the poofy girl hair talking about weather, every word clear as the day he **was promising**.
- 9) Chicho nodded his head, like he **was believing** the lies. "Okay, so tell me why I should make the switch.
- 10) We're going to carry out a full autopsy, of course, but I thought you'd be interested because he **was showing** symptoms of some infection.
- 11) But, that all of those people that saw that trauma won't necessarily think that they need to seek out help. And he **was hoping** we could all spread the message that if you were one of those people, you should definitely do that
- 12) On hearing her voice, Ucok said: "Ma, please come and take me. I want to go back to Aceh. "Jamaliah asked where he **was staying**, and Ucok replied that he had no home, not even a blanket.
- 13) I knew what he **was thinking** because I had thought it myself on numerous occasions.

- 14) The old man stood on the sidewalk and belted out melodies I doubt he'd thought of in thirty years. In his mind he **was standing** on the stage, and it wasn't long before his laughter mixed with his tears, proving that glass can't lose its co
- 15) . He tweeted that it was an illegal leak, a felony, and he was going to ask for an FBI investigation. And he put Reince Priebus, the chief of staff's Twitter handle on his message, as if he **was suggesting** that Priebus was somehow involved with this.
- 16) I would lie down there, and like he did, pull the crust off slices, then ball up the soft middle part to make bread dough, and I found I liked eating it that way as much as he **was liking** it up above me.
- 17) Remembering Matt's poor little ghost face across the table, she hoped he **was feeling** better. She ended up on a bench in a small park.
- 18) But after talking to him, I could see he **was loving** every minute of it.
- 19) I read it and I thought it was quirky and odd and a little disturbing and funny. It really appealed to me. He **was surprising** me all through the play. And it was an opportunity to work with Morris as the director.
- 20) He did start to get a little bit irritated that night. he was starting to get hungry, maybe. He **was wanting** his warm doggie bed, and he was kind of wondering why we were camping in this weird spot.

Second Category (Correct)

- 1) The noise surprised me
- 2) **Didn't believe the** news yesterday.
- 3) I **wanted** to go to the cinema yesterday.
- 4) **Did** you **hear** music? (10)
- 5) He **stayed** at the scene until police arrived.
- 6) Experience **showed** that when governments knew their costs they could work to manage their costs and make their services competitive with outside contractors (Weiss, 1997).
- 7) I just **liked** the fact it was a great atmosphere all the time.
- 8) The police **knew** that Hicks and Peyton both lived in the small apartment, and they were thus on notice that some spaces in the apartment might be used exclusively by Peyton.
- 9) "When I talked to her, it **seemed** like she enjoyed it and she seemed happy, " Reisinger said.
- 10) I **didn't feel** that this was a good idea.
- 11) The carrier **promised** to provide new cars in exchange for the damaged cars.
- 12) Mr. Perry **suggested** that the United States might resort to air strikes against Iraq even if Iraqi troops never crossed into Iraq.
- 13) Every day was like a great experience for me. I just **loved** it.
- 14) This book **belonged** to my grandmother.
- 15) Ogene said in February that the school **hoped** for a fairer hearing from new Education Secretary Betsy DeVos.
- 16) **The judges thought that those limited benefits did not justify the costs. Just as the Supreme Court recognized in Turner.**

- 17) I **didn't understand** this questio
- 18) He **resumed** his seat.
- 19) When President Obama **stood** on the steps on the Capitol eight years from next week, the budget deficit was \$1.4 trillion.
- 20) I **saw** him in Oconee County, and he didn't ask any questions.

Third Category (incorrect)

- 1) The noise **was surprising** me. (4)
- 2) They **were liking** to travel in vineyards across the globe
- 3) I **wasn't believing** the news.
- 4) she **was suggesting** in Part I, the approach we propose is to punish offenders in the types of cases discussed in Part III only for criminal behaviour within their control, and not for any statutory harms that ultimately result from their actions
- 5) He **was promising** he would not allow any refugees to be placed in any town that didn't want them there.
- 6) I **was not feeling** that this was a good idea.
- 7) This book **was belonging** to my grandmother.
- 8) Campanelli said she also **was hoping** having public defenders involved at an earlier stage would result in more cases being disposed of quickly.
- 9) They both **were loving** modern art; he was a retired postal worker.
- 10) **Were you hearing** the music?
- 11) Jones **was staying** down on the field for a second, until teammates came over and gathered around him.
- 12) The year 1982 **was seeing** the founding of the American Bankruptcy Institute (ABI).
- 13) So this is exactly the life that I **was thinking** I would have.
- 14) She **was resuming** her journalistic writing during the '70s and early' 80s
- 15) My hamamelis is just ready to bloom, and the dogs **were enjoying** a mild (though muddy) walk.
- 16) Data **was showing** that Republican appointees were significantly more likely to agree with the retribution theory question.
- 17) I **was wanting** to go to the cinema yesterday.
- 18) I **was not understanding** this question
- 19) I **was standing**, opened the door, and held out my hand to him.
- 20) I never **was knowing** my grandfather spoke that language fluently.